

Exponential Equations:

Harald Schröder

2019

We view the following exponential equation:

$$k, A, C, E, G, I \in \mathbb{R}^+$$

$$A \cdot Bx^4 \cdot C \cdot Dx^3 \cdot E \cdot Fx^2 \cdot G \cdot Hx \cdot I^j = k$$

$$B, D, F, H, j \in \mathbb{R}$$

We use the Briggsian logarithm (lg):

$$\begin{aligned} (\lg A) \cdot Bx^4 + (\lg C) \cdot Dx^3 + (\lg E) \cdot Fx^2 + (\lg G) \cdot Hx \\ + (\lg I) \cdot j = \lg(k) \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have reduced the exponential equation of order 4 to one polynomial of order 4. The polynomial of order 4 can be solved with Bronstein [1] chapter 2.4.2.3 p.131-134. The general solution for a polynomial

$$ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + e = 0 \quad a, b, c, d, e \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$a \neq 0$$

is the following:

First we construct with the substitution $y = x + (b/(4a))$ the reduced polynomial:

$$y^4 + py^2 + qy + r = 0 \quad p, q, r \in \mathbb{R}$$

Then we view the cubic resolvent:

$$z^3 + 2pz^2 + (p^2 - 4r) \cdot z - q^2 = 0$$

with the solutions z_1, z_2, z_3 . The solutions of the reduced polynomial of order 4 can be presented as:

$$y_1 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\sqrt{z_1} + \sqrt{z_2} - \sqrt{z_3})$$

$$y_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\sqrt{z_1} - \sqrt{z_2} + \sqrt{z_3})$$

$$y_3 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-\sqrt{z_1} + \sqrt{z_2} + \sqrt{z_3})$$

$$y_4 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-\sqrt{z_1} - \sqrt{z_2} - \sqrt{z_3})$$

For the solutions of the cubic resolvent we need the condition:

$$\sqrt{z_1} \cdot \sqrt{z_2} \cdot \sqrt{z_3} = q$$

We occupy with the general polynomial of order 3:

$$ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d = 0 \quad r = \frac{b}{a} \quad a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R} \quad a \neq 0$$

With the substitution $y = x + (r/3)$ we get the reduced polynomial of order 3:

$$y^3 + py + q = 0 \quad p, q \in \mathbb{R}$$

This polynomial can be solved with Cardan's method. The accurate solution is done at Schröder [2] chapter 13. The solutions can be real or complex numbers.

In a similar way we can reduce exponential equations of order N to polynomials of order N.

References:

[1] = Bronstein, Semendjajew „Taschenbuch der Mathematik“, Teubner Verlag, Leipsic, 22. edition 1985

[2] = Harald Schröder „Trigonometric problem cases well solved“, Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin 2001